

The Mechanical Performance of Additive Manufactured Silica Lattice Structures

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Abstract. The current study investigates the performance of Additive Manufactured (AM) silica (SiO₂) scaffolds using advanced lattice designs. In particular, six specific lattice design structures based on Strut-Lattice Structures and on Triply Periodic Minimal Structures (TPMS) were additively manufactured by utilising the Stereolithography method. Initially, the mechanical and morphological behaviour of solid 3D printed specimens was studied using characterization techniques, such as instrumented nanoindentation and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) in order to understand the material behaviour. Then, the AM complex lattice structures were tested under a quasi-static uniaxial compression loading in order to reveal their mechanical response, which is depended on their relative density and also to deduce the stress strain response. The results have shown that all structures presented extensive degradation in mechanical behaviour due to the influence of scaling laws and the existing porosity in the structure originated from the manufacturing procedure. However, strut-structures exhibited more severe deterioration in their mechanical properties compared with TPMS structures. This mechanical study of AM ceramic lattice structures is an essential step prior to further exploration and research of the ceramic 3D printed lattice scaffolds in tissue engineering.

Keywords: Lattice Structures, Additive Manufacturing, Stereolithography, Ceramic, Mechanical Properties.

1 Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) or otherwise 3D printing has gained great momentum over the preceding decade in numerous fields, providing cutting-edge technologies for 3D model fabrication, by depositing consecutive layers of material [1]. One of the most accurate AM technique is Stereolithography (SLA), which utilizes liquid photo-reactive polymer resins to create 3D structures of unprecedented topological and geomet-

rical complexity [1-2]. This versatility in design created enormous potentialities in various applications, especially in biomechanical engineering for tissue scaffold fabrication by applying complex lattice structures [3-6]. In particular, according to Mahmoud [7], lattice structures present numerous advantages for tissue engineering, such as high porosity and high surface area to volume ratio. These attributes enable blood and nutrients' diffusion inside the human body, resulting in healing acceleration and improved tissue regeneration. For this reason, it is crucial to investigate and implement lattice structures in order to validate their biological and mechanical performance and enhance their applicability in tissue scaffold fabrication.

Numerous research efforts have articulated the integration of AM technologies in the medical sector, regarding tissue engineering and porous implant fabrication, utilizing miscellaneous biocompatible materials, including metals, ceramics, or polymers. However, the necessity of biocompatible materials, in terms of implementing complex lattice structures for scaffold fabrication that provide enhanced mechanical stability and robustness still remains an open and challenging issue, requiring further research.

This study approaches such research issues by employing lattice structures for scaffold fabrication, based on ceramic Silica (SiO_2) resin, using the SLA technique. More specifically, six lattice structures were designed and constructed in three different relative densities (20%, 30%, 40%). Initially, material characterization of the 3D printed ceramic samples was performed via Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and nanoindentation. Then, the mechanical response of the 3D printed structures was extracted by applying a quasi-static uniaxial compression loading. Finally, the acquired data were exploited to calculate the influence of the relative density on each structure's strength.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Design, 3D Printing and Post-Processing of Ceramic Lattice Scaffolds

In this study, six lattice structures were designed via Solidworks™ and nTopology™ design and engineering software programs. Such advanced design structures have an enormous potential in biomechanical applications, especially for tissue regeneration purposes [6-10]. Three of the structures are classified into Strut-lattice structure family and the other three into Triply Periodic Minimal Structures family (TPMS). The Strut-lattices include Octet, Rhombic dodecahedron (RD) and Re-entrant (RE) designs, while the TPMS structures consist of Gyroid, Schwarz Diamond (SD) and Schwarz Primitive (SP) sheet designs. These design structures present unique characteristics and provide different properties, such as high porosity, high surface area to volume ratio, advanced strength, and high energy absorption rate [7-10]. In order to select the most suitable structure that satisfies the mechanical requirements for tissue engineering, three different relative densities (20%, 30%, 40%) of each structure are examined to extract their overall mechanical response through scaling laws. Furthermore, compression cubic specimens of 10mm were chosen according to the ISO-10545. The unit cell length was selected to achieve symmetric structures at 5mm. The wall thickness influenced the

relative density and varied from 0.5mm to 1mm. **Fig. 1** illustrates indicative specimens of the lattice structures under study.

Fig. 1. Samples of 30% relative density for a) Strut-lattice structures: Octet, Rhombic Dodecahedron, Re-Entrant and b) TPMS lattice structures: Gyroid, Schwarz Diamond (SD) and Primitive (SP)

The 3D printing process was performed via Formlabs Form 2, enabling high accuracy down to $50\mu\text{m}$ for all specimens. A composite resin with polymeric matrix of silica (SiO_2) reinforcement was used as feedstock material. To achieve the desired dimensions of each specimen after firing to burn away the polymer matrix, the 3D models were scaled up 1.123 times, based on the manufacturer's guidelines. Solid cubic samples were fabricated for mechanical testing and calibration while nanoindentation samples, with dimensions $5 \times 30 \times 5 \text{mm}^3$, were also manufactured for material characterization. All specimens were printed at least three times to measure the repeatability of the results. Subsequently, the 3D printed samples were fired in a BOX-AM10-1700 (Thermansys) furnace inside a crucible, where the polymer matrix was burnt away and the samples were transformed into pure silica ceramic parts. The firing schedule was provided by the resin's manufacturer with maximum temperature up to 1250°C .

2.2 Material Characterization & Mechanical Testing

Material characterization and testing was conducted on pure silica constructs (after burning) to evaluate the attained quality of the 3D printed ceramic material. Particularly, for microstructure and morphology examination, the Phenom ProX Desktop SEM system was utilized. For the evaluation of the elastic modulus of the 3D printed material, nanoindentation was performed using a dynamic Ultra Micro Hardness Tester (SHIMADZU DUH-211S). The applied force of the indenter was 200mN and five distinct measurements were scattered on the surface of the samples. To extract the stress-strain response of the ceramic material and the lattice structures, a quasi-static uniaxial compression loading was performed utilizing a universal testing machine (M500-50AT Testometric Company, UK). Due to low strength and brittle behavior of the ceramic material, the mechanical testing was employed with a 500N load cell and a cross-head speed of 1mm/min was applied.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 3D Printing & Material Characterization Process

Fig. 2 depicts typical images of 3D printed ceramic scaffolds, after firing, for all the examined lattice structures at relative density of 30%. The 3D printed specimens presented high quality and good geometric tolerance at each lattice geometry with only slightly micro-flaws due to the removal of the support structures.

Fig. 2. 3D printed ceramic scaffolds of 30% relative density

Solid cubic samples were fabricated and examined to characterize the 3D printed silica material. The mass of each specimen was measured and a slight difference was found versus the density provided by the manufacturer. According to SEM images as shown in **Fig. 3**, small to medium pores of entrapped gases were identified due to the firing process. More specifically, the porosity of 3D printed and fired silica was measured at 20.26%. Subsequently, severe degradation in mechanical properties was expected to occur. Indeed, the mean value of the elastic modulus was evaluated to be 43.3 ± 0.5 GPa by nanoindentation process. The compressive peak strength of solid cubic samples was determined to be at 16 ± 0.5 MPa.

Fig. 3. SEM images of 3D printed silica (SiO_2) with SLA technique utilizing: a) Backscattered Electron Detector (BSD) and b) Secondary Electron Detector (SED)

3.2 Mechanical Behavior of Lattice Scaffolds

After acquiring the basic mechanical properties for 3D printed solid silica, the next step was the evaluation of lattices' mechanical response. In **Table 1**, the effective elastic modulus and the effective peak strength are listed for each lattice structure in three distinct densities, namely at 20%, 30% and 40% (as-designed relative density). According to the literature [7], lattice structures comply with specific scaling laws connecting the effective properties with the relative density. These laws are formulated as follows:

$$\frac{E_{lat}}{E_{solid}} = C_E \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{n_e} \text{ and } \frac{\sigma_{peak,lat}}{\sigma_{peak,solid}} = C_\sigma \cdot (\bar{\rho})^{n_\sigma} \quad (1) \text{ and } (2)$$

where E_{lat} and $\sigma_{peak,lat}$ are the effective elastic modulus and peak strength for lattices, respectively; the E_{solid} and the $\sigma_{peak,solid}$ correspond to the material, while C_E , C_σ , n_e and n_σ are the constants that depend on the applied lattice structures. The values of these constants are demonstrated in **Table 1**. Gyroid and RE structures exhibited low effective elastic modulus almost three times lower than the SD structures, which possess the highest elastic modulus values.

Table 1. Values of Effective-Elastic-Modulus and Effective-Peak-Stress for each specimen and the constants of scaling laws corresponding to the structure

Properties		Elastic Modulus (MPa)			Peak Stress (MPa)		
Structures	Rel. density	20%	30%	40%	20%	30%	40%
Gyroid		2114	2946	4023	1.06	1.65	3.65
S. Diamond		4375	8997	12353	3.29	4.59	10.3
S. Primitive		1739	3172	5172	0.40	0.92	1.80
Octet		3701	4933	7181	0.43	0.74	1.12
Re-entrant		1818	3243	4858	0.59	1.20	2.23
Rhombic dodecahedron		2333	5384	9543	0.36	0.69	1.19
Structures	Constants	C_E	n_e	C_σ	n_σ		
Gyroid		0.221	0.959	1.625	2.168		
S. Diamond		0.979	1.329	4.176	2.070		
S. Primitive		0.519	1.610	0.874	2.242		
Octet		0.485	1.170	0.260	1.431		
Re-entrant		0.408	1.409	0.949	2.092		
Rhombic dodecahedron		1.376	1.999	0.414	1.871		

Fig. 4 shows the engineering stress-strain diagrams for all lattice structures at 30% relative density. Regarding **Table 1** and **Fig. 4**, the superiority of TPMS structures in terms of strength was observed at all relative density values, especially for the SD structure reaching up to 10.3MPa peak stress. The strut-lattices revealed reduced mechanical strength, especially at low relative densities (<30%). However, the strut-lattice

achieved comparable performance with the TPMS specimens in terms of elastic modulus, particularly the RD structure. It is worth noting that all structures tended to show behavior closer to stretching-dominated ($\nu < 2$) [10], due to the nature of the material and the manufacturing process. Finally, the high porosity of material triggers microfractures inside the structure of the samples that appear as discontinuities on the stress-strain diagram.

Fig. 4. Engineering stress-strain diagram for all test specimens at 30% relative density

4 Conclusions

This paper presented a study for the mechanical behavior of 3D printed ceramic lattice structures using Stereolithography. Six lattice structures were manufactured using Silica (SiO_2) resin. The material was evaluated through nanoindentation testing and Scanning Electron Microscopy, which revealed that the porosity of the material was high, leading to degradation in basic mechanical properties. Also, the mechanical response of each lattice structure was extracted and the scaling law was calculated in order to express the relation between the mechanical properties and the relative density. The TPMS structures achieved enhanced mechanical behavior, especially the SD structure of 40% relative density which has shown remarkable peak strength at 10.3MPa and elastic modulus at 12353MPa. On the other hand, strut-lattices revealed lower mechanical strength and elastic modulus comparable with TPMS structures. Finally, it is essential for future research to modify and optimize the firing procedure in order to achieve extensive reduction of porosity regarding the 3D printed material.

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